

CLARIAH data Stories Editor: an open interactive environment to create and publish data-driven research narratives

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Background

Scholarly writing in the Humanities and Social Sciences (SSH) has been greatly influenced by innovative models of scholarly publishing in the scientific domains (for example in the Life Sciences (Chavan & Penev, 2011 as cited by Nury et al., 2022), where practices in sharing and reusing data in the context of the FAIR principles and Open Science have matured in the past years originating and moving forward the field of *semantic publishing*.

Semantic publishing means that a scholarly or scientific paper goes beyond a flat single layer of text, images and tables, and becomes a multi-dimensional, “actionable” aggregate of narrative, data and visualizations that are also machine readable (Girka, 2016). This is important to academic publishing, since it facilitates not only reproducibility but also transparency, since both the provenance of the data and the layers of interpretation added to it can be traced (Nury et al., 2022).

Moreover, since all the elements in semantic publications become machine readable, an additional application is the generation of automatic “styling” for final publication. Beek et al. (2024) call this type of approach the “FAIR data paper”¹. An additional added value of the *data paper* is that it makes it possible “to give credit for the effort required to prepare, curate, and contextualize data with the proper metadata” (Nury et al., 2022).

¹ The proof of concept set up by Beek et al., (2024) uses the RASH framework (Research Articles in Simplified HTML), which relies on open web standards like HTML and CSS, they demonstrate how to re-implement a version of a paper in the style used by many journals and conferences in the computer science domain, acknowledging, however, that academic styles are not typically made available in a CSS format in the SSH domain.

This tendency in semantic publishing coincides with a trend in journalism, where *data stories* “are becoming widely accepted as the output of a process that is in many aspects similar to that of a computational scholar: gaining insights by analyzing data sets using (semi-)automatized methods and presenting these insights using (interactive) visualizations and other textual outputs based on data” (Ordelman et al., 2022).

Different initiatives in the SSH domain have appeared which facilitate the publication of *data papers* or *data stories*, for example, the Journal of Open Humanities Data² started publishing data papers in 2015, or the most recent Journal of Digital History³, launched in 2021.

To create *data papers* or *data stories*, researchers need to use an *editor* that makes it possible to write (in the traditional sense) and add connections to the source data, perform processes on the data, and display results of queries and visualizations. A typical tool to do this would be, for example, a jupyter notebook⁴. However, setting it up, using it and publishing it may be a cumbersome task for some researchers in the SSH domain. In addition, as Beek et al. (2024) and Ordelman et al. (2022) indicate, the technology used by notebooks or virtual machines may not use open standards, and may not be able to access all the data that could potentially be only available via closed APIs that require authentication.

One of the main aims of the CLARIAH project⁵ was to create a sustainable infrastructure that would support researchers in the SSH in sharing their data in a more transparent and reusable way, adhering to the FAIR principles⁶. The final aim is, however, that scholarly findings can be more widely communicated. Since the *data paper* is becoming an established form of scholarly writing (Nury et al., 2022), and *data stories* have gained momentum as a way to communicate data-driven research, significant efforts have been invested in providing researchers with the facilities to create semantic publications. One of these efforts⁷ is the *CLARIAH data stories editor*, an open source and free environment to create and publish data-driven research narratives, which we propose to showcase to the DH Benelux community.

DEMONSTRATION

In this demo we will show how the *CLARIAH data stories editor* works in practice for the end user (the researchers in SSH). We will focus on:

- introducing the general options for setting up any of the two web-based setups and their workspaces

² <https://openhumanitiesdata.metajnl.com/>

³ <https://journalofdigitalhistory.org/en>

⁴ <https://docs.jupyter.org/en/latest/>

⁵ <https://www.clariah.nl/>

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/FAIR_data

⁷ Different work packages within CLARIAH have created data stories and papers: <https://stories.datalegend.net/>; <https://mediasuitedatastories.clariah.nl/>, their efforts convey in the CLARIAH data stories editor.

- building a data story: showing how *any* researcher can build a narrative where text, data and media are fully integrated
 - Note: there is no need to know a programming language, e.g. python, to create a data story; only the query language for the type of data, e.g. SPARQL, although over time this requirement might also be weakened by the use of query builders.
- integrating data: connecting to SPARQL endpoints (from any triple store).
 - *Note: In the near future, it will connect to APIs from relational databases.*
- running processes with the data as an actionable part of the story
- adding and editing queries and visualizations.

The *CLARIAH data stories editor* has been used in co-development with researchers during the CLARIAH project. Different versions of this specific editor have been used for demonstration and testing purposes. The latest stable version will be released in 2025 on <https://datastories.sd.di.huc.knaw.nl/> and <https://stories.clariah.nl/>.

The screenshot shows the CLARIAH Data Stories editor interface. At the top, there is a dark blue header with the CLARIAH logo and 'Data Stories' on the left, and 'Rob Zeeman' on the right. The main content area has a title 'The 1918-19 flu epidemic in The Netherlands' and is attributed to 'Thomas de Groot, Wouter Beek'. Below the title, there is a license link: 'http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/'.

The interface features a sidebar on the left with icons for adding (+), editing (pencil), and deleting (trash) blocks. The main content area contains a narrative block titled 'The dataset' with the following text:

Thanks to the indexation efforts of archives and the [LINKS project](#), large parts of the Dutch civil registry (*Burgerlijke Stand*) are now becoming available for historians. The death certificates used here are retrieved from [openarch.nl](#) (available [here](#)). From the individual death certificates files per archive, one combined dataset was created. One challenge of working with these certificates is that that the same certificate may have been indexed by more than one archive. These were de-duplicated using a combination of date of death, location and similar full names (using string distances). Key variables were subsequently cleaned and standardized, such as age at death, placenames, and occupations. Using different string match combinations, place names were standardized against the [Historical Dutch Toponyms dataset](#), to retrieve coordinates and Amsterdam Codes. Occupations were matched against the file [HSN Occupations](#) to retrieve HISCO, HISCLASS and HISCAM categorizations. All related R scripts can be found at our [Github repository](#). The dataset was then converted into Linked Data with [COW](#), using the "Persons table" datamodel designed by Gerrit Bloothoof and Kees Mandemakers in the LINKS project. The complete Linked Dataset and the related metadata scheme can be explored at [Druid](#). The table below demonstrates the success of the standardization efforts, presented as Linked Data.

Below the narrative block, there is a data table with the following structure:

	year	n_deceased	percent_coded_placenames	percent_coded_occupations
1	"1910"	"79575"	"97.8913"	"94.2689"
2	"1911"	"86727"	"97.9499"	"94.6854"

Figure 1. Some of the features: adding blocks of narrative and data.

Because archives generally decide for themselves which variables from the civil registry they will index, occupations of the deceased are not available for all regions. Archives from the provinces of Drenthe, Gelderland, and Zeeland are, regrettably, the only ones to have structurally indexed all occupations of the deceased for this period.

Share of known occupations of the deceased, aged eighteen and over, by municipality:

Total deaths in The Netherlands by month:

Figure 2. Data visualization inside the editor

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